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PRESS RELEASE

Joint Communication StandICT.eu 2023 & ASHVIN

Identification of Pressing Priorities in the Standardization of Digital Twin Technologies

Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) signed between ASHVIN & StandICT.eu 2023

Brussels, 22 March 2021 - StandICT.eu 2023 & ASHVIN announces their collaboration boosting open standardisation for Digital Twins at a European scale. The StandICT.eu 2023 - a Coordination & Support Action supported under the European Commission Framework Programme of H2020^{1t} - is enthusiastic having signed a MoU with the **ASHVIN that is a Horizon 2020 RIA initiative.**

StandICT.eu 2023 has two key axes - firstly, it will fund **400+ European standardisation experts** in a series of 10 Open calls providing a total of 3M€ of funding. Secondly, it launches the **European Observatory for ICT Standardisation (EUOS)** that is an interactive online ecosystem including an up-to-date standards repository as well as working groups sharing insights about ongoing standardization efforts across different initiatives. StandICT.eu 2023 focuses on horizontal and vertical ICT fields as defined in the Rolling Plan for ICT Standardisation², one of the focuses are **Digital Twins and Smart Cities.**

ASHVIN aims at enabling the European construction industry to significantly improve its productivity, while reducing cost and ensuring absolutely safe work conditions, by providing a proposal for a European wide digital twin standard, an open source digital twin platform integrating IoT and image technologies, and a set of tools and demonstrated procedures to apply the platform and the standard proven to guarantee specified productivity, cost, and safety improvements. Specific to standardization, **ASHVIN** will develop a proposal for a **European wide standard for digital twin technologies in the construction industry.** The standard will be based upon an inventory of European and International standards (existing and under development) including the standardization areas such as IoT, BIM, AI, Digital Twin, Drones and Robotics etc.

The MoU can consolidate even further this commitment.

¹ StandICT.eu 2023 runs from 1st September 2020 for a 36-month period. The Consortium of Partners includes Trust-IT SRL (Coordinator), Dublin City University and Australo Interinnov Marketing Lab SL.

²https://ec.europa.eu/growth/single-market/european-standards/ict-standardisation_en

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“For achieving the expected project results and enhancing their impact on the market, Austrian Standards International, as the main standardization partner in ASHVIN, supports the project through identifying standards – existing and under development – that are most important and key. Next to the identification, an essential part of our work is the analysis of gaps in standards and how these gaps can be closed. One mean to do so is the active contribution to standardization, either to trigger the revision of existing standards or proposing new standards. The collaboration between the two initiatives (StandICT.eu and ASHVIN) is an excellent chance to enable ASHVIN technical partners to participate in the identified and prioritized standardization activities, especially in the domains of IoT, BIM and Digital Twin. This and the European Observatory for ICT Standardisation will boost ASHVIN's dissemination and exploitation activities through standards and standardisation” believes **Dr Karl Gruen** (Director Standards Development,) from Austrian Standards International, a key ASHVIN partner.

“As a project manager in varied ICT innovation projects, I am familiar with the challenges related to standardization of the innovation outcomes. I truly believe that the research projects, like ASHVIN, can benefit from the StandICT.eu as it offers more direct funding for standardisation activities, but also it provides an easy-access to ICT standardization documents that can be useful resources for innovation management” - believes **Mona Marill**, project Manager at AUSTRALO Marketing Lab, a StandICT.eu 2023 partner - *“Moreover, we hope that other ICT initiatives find the EUOS online working groups useful for engaging with new stakeholders and experts as well as for disseminating their standardization outcomes”*.

One of the critical efforts of the coming StandICT.eu 2023 months will result in delivering landscape & gap analysis as well as policy papers from the top-notch experts dealing with standardisation in the fields of Smart Cities and Digital Twins. The goal is to effectively highlight the most pressing priorities to be addressed to the European Policy makers, the international Standardisation Organization [SDOs] and to National Standardisation Bodies [NSBs]. With this regard, the signature of this Memorandum establishes a trustworthy collaboration between StandICT.eu 2023 and ASHVIN.

For more information & contact of **StandICT.eu**

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